

THE INTRODUCTION OF AN INTERMEDIATE CHARACTER INTO THE BINARY OPPOSITION "FRIEND OR FOE" AS A NECESSARY ELEMENT OF A LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT

The article is concerned with the variants of representation of the binary opposition "friend/foe"; it is traced how its logical transformation into the triad "another - one's own - a friend" takes place. The importance of the influence of the "place identity" on the emergence of the "psychological and moral" crisis of the hero Captain Scott, when nationally "us" becomes "strangers", is noted. Within the framework of the article, a complex of linguistic means was considered that actualize the opposition "friend/foe" and evaluative vocabulary and pronouns (we, us, our, they, you and I) were also analyzed.

KEY WORDS: opposition "friend/foe", concept "Englishman", concepts: "another", "tolerance", "place" "identity".

J. Aldridge's novel "I don't want him to die", created in 1957, continues to develop the oriental theme in the writer's work. Traditionally, in addition to the theme, is the choice of a hero - a rebel, an extraordinary Englishman who does not recognize the imperial policy of Great Britain. This novel could be written only by a person who deeply and professionally knows the whole political knot of the problems of military Egypt, evaluates the presence of the British army and the emerging national liberation movement in the country. Therefore, the binary opposition "friend/foe", defined by T. V. Aliyeva as "conceptual opposition", is explored in the novel "I don't want him to die" from political and socio-psychological positions. We consider the installation of V.V. Krasnykh about the process of conceptual analysis "From concept to text and back": "From a substantive point of view, by concept we understand the deep meaning, the folded semantic structure of the text, which is the embodiment of intention (deep psychological reaction to an external stimulus) - through it the motive of the author's activity" (Krasnykh, 1998:57). The development of the concepts "friend/foe" within the binary opposition is indeed the "starting point" for the creation of this novel, because the plot is based on their opposition. By adding the concept of "other", J. Aldridge develops a psychological connotation in the interpretation of the concept of "alien", focusing on the degree of tolerance of Captain Scott. Representatives of cognitive literary criticism operate with terms

as tools for interpreting a text precisely from such research positions: "When creating a text, the concept becomes the main one ... on which the semantic, cognitive and compositional structure of the text depends" (Vitkovskaya, 2012: 38). We must agree with this, since the binary opposition is also embedded in the system of characters in this novel. The protagonist of the novel is Captain Scott, who has lived in Egypt for a long time, a specialist in the military topographic service, considers his immediate superior, General Church, a criminal "he has blood on his hands." The concepts of "friend/foe" are the basis that cements the main conflict.

1. The first conflict takes place formally between "their own": Captain Scott and General Church, who is responsible for the death of a detachment of the English army. After such a betrayal by a senior leader, Captain Scott feels like a "stranger" in his own army. J. Aldridge cites a dialogue with Colonel Peacock in which opposition is given with the help of pronouns: "It worries me when your brother while inventing assignments for us and now you are demanding that we complete a certain task" (Aldridge, 1957: 6). This paradox, when representatives of the same nationality, bound by army duty and an oath to the English crown, are so divided into "You and Us", which is associated with the division of "us and foes".

2. J. Aldridge creates a binary opposition for the heroes working in different "spaces", which determine their political views and the real alignment of military forces in Egypt: the desert and Cairo. The military authorities in Cairo and the British soldiers dying in the criminal negligence of their orders: "Admit it, this whole company in Cairo seems to you a bunch of disgusting churches" (Aldridge, 1957: 18).

Summing up, it can be noted that the symbol of the whole complex of "alien" - (military, political, moral) is General Church in Scott's perception. The writer cites a situation when, after the death of the Pickering detachment, in violation of any subordination, an accusation occurs: "Scott lost his temper and called him a bloody killer.

-Did Church hear that?

-Half of the army heard that" (Aldridge, 1957: 21).

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